

SPECTRUM MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE AND REGULATIONS
IN THE U.S. - DO WE NEED A CHANGE
IN THE TWENTY FIRST CENTURY?

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ABSTRACT

The spectrum management regulations, procedures and structure in the U.S. are a result of the Communications Act of 1934, the changes made to the basic Act, growth of telecommunications nationally and internationally, and the adaptability of spectrum management to accompany the growth in use and technology. This growth has required more national and international spectrum management meetings and conferences to address future radiocommunication requirements, and better technical ways to ensure minimum interference. The U.S. needs to consider additional changes to the spectrum management structure, processes, and regulations that will make telecommunication leadership more effective, address new user requirements in a more effective and timely manner, and promote new spectrum efficient technologies in the Twenty First Century.

Introduction

The spectrum management structure in the United States is unique in the world in that it consists of three interrelated elements. These elements consist of the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) that manages the private or non-government telecommunications and the associated spectrum; the National Telecommunications and Information Administration (NTIA) that sets Federal telecommunication policies and manages the Federal Governments use of the spectrum; and the Department of State (DOS) that coordinates international negotiations with the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) and individual countries as required (Figure 1). Adding to this complexity the FCC reports to the Congress of the United States and NTIA reports to the President of the United States (Figure 2). In order to obtain requirements for use of the radio frequency spectrum, the FCC resorts to Public Notice of Inquiries (NOI's) while the NTIA directly contacts Federal Government agencies through the Interdepartment Radio Advisory Committee (IRAC) representatives. The system in the U.S. is contrasted with that in most countries in which there is a single government agency, such as the Post Telecommunications and Telegraph (PTT) or a Ministry of Posts and Telecommunications (MPT). The government agency in these countries deals with user requirements and international negotiations.

Can the U.S. in the Twenty First Century continue to use a system of management that appears to be more complex than the

corresponding systems in the rest of the world? Can the U.S. management system respond in a timely manner to new user requirements that are driven by new technology developments, considering the separation of the U.S. structure, the difficulty of obtaining and coordinating user requirements and the difficulty of coordinating spectrum availability between the government and non-government users? This paper summarizes preliminary views of the authors concerning the results of an investigation of the U.S. spectrum management structure; and, in particular, the adoption of new management and planning methods to introduce new technology requirements in a more timely manner.

Figure 1 International Radio Coordination

Figure 2. National Spectrum Management

Spectrum Growth

In the past ten years there has been significant growth of the telecommunications manufacturing and service industries, and a large growth in telecommunication and radiocommunication consumer products. In these areas, billions of dollars have been invested and hundreds of thousands of jobs have evolved. This expansion will continue so long as consumer demands continue. One of the yardsticks that can be used to indicate spectrum use growth in the private sector and the Federal government is the increase in the station authorizations by the FCC and the number of frequency assignment authorizations by the NTIA as shown in Figure 3. As of 1980, the FCC had approved 1,812,619 station authorizations to private radio and broadcast users. In only eight years, this has grown to 2,770,651 for a increase of 52.9%. For the Federal government, the increase in frequency assignment authorizations over the same time period was 46.1%. Based on this information, in 16 more years, the growth will be 100%. Is the spectrum management process capable of satisfying these future requirements?

Figure 3. Spectrum Use and Resources Growth

What has been the history of the FCC and NTIA to meet their obligations to satisfy the past ten years of growth in spectrum requirements? Obviously, both agencies have satisfied the vast majority of the spectrum requirements and are undertaking major efforts to accommodate new technologies such as HDTV, domestic satellites, mobile satellites, etc. It stands to reason that if the demand increases, the workload to satisfy that demand will increase, and therefore the cost to manage the system will also increase. This appears to be the case at the FCC. As shown in Figure 3, the FCC was appropriated \$75,992,000 in 1980. In 1988, their appropriation grew to \$99,613,000. This is a growth of 31.1%. At this rate in 16 years, the FCC requirements will be about \$162 million, assuming the demand increases as shown above. This has not been the case with the Federal government. As shown in Figure 3, the NTIA has actually decreased its appropriation from

\$18,467,000 in 1980 to \$14,560,000 in 1988 for a growth of -21.2%. NTIA has managed to decrease its resources while its workload to manage the spectrum increased as shown above. One reason for this is that NTIA has upgraded its ability (Automated Data Processing (ADP), instituting a 5 year review program, and minimizing regulations and procedures) to handle larger and more complex spectrum management workloads. Therefore, it can be concluded that growth in spectrum use in the next 16 years in both the private sector and the Federal government will continue. Solutions other than increasing NTIA's and FCC's budgets will have to be attempted to: (1) focus their efforts individually and jointly in becoming more effective in their management of the spectrum; (2) consider new strategies such as adapting more automated means to their processes, establishing common data bases, developing long range plans, and considering common ADP systems; (3) consider new incentives for the users to use the spectrum efficiently by promoting spectrum saving technologies, etc.; (4) and consider structural or organizational changes to the Communications Act.

Regulatory Procedures

The telecommunication management procedures and structure in the United States have been primarily governed by the Communication Act of 1934 as amended.² The Communication Act provides for both ownership and operation of telecommunications facilities by private entities and the U.S. Government. Concern over the impact of private radio use prompted Congress to establish the Federal Communications Commission (FCC). The FCC's jurisdiction over private sector and state and local government communication was granted for coordination and licensing purposes. Control and regulation of federal radio use was assigned to the President. Although Congress divided the responsibility for spectrum management between the President and the FCC, it did not divide the spectrum resource itself. The FCC and the President have the authority to make independent spectrum-related decisions including the assignment of frequencies for specific use.

In 1978, the President delegated his authority to manage the spectrum used by the Federal Government to the Secretary of Commerce through Executive Order 12046.³ The Secretary of Commerce further delegated this authority, under Department of Commerce (DOC) Organizational Order 10-10,⁴ to the Assistant Secretary for Communications and Information, who is also the head of the National Telecommunications and Information Administration (NTIA).

Although the FCC and NTIA operate independently, their common concerns about interference and increased demand for RF spectrum require close coordination. The decisions by one affects spectrum use by constituents of the other. Therefore, the FCC and NTIA jointly develop the "National Table of Frequency Allocations." In this table, some bands are designated for exclusive use by the Federal Government, while others are

designated for exclusive use by the nonfederal sector. However, most bands are shared.

Because NTIA and the FCC have fundamentally different missions, their specific approach to spectrum management differs. They maintain separate technical standards, data bases, and procedures to carry out their own spectrum management responsibilities. Since the FCC grants nonfederal use of the spectrum, its decision-making processes are open to public participation and court review. Its policy decisions on the use of particular frequency bands are governed by the rulemaking requirements of the Administrative Procedures Act.⁵ NTIA, on the other hand, seeks the advice of Federal Government agencies through the Interdepartment Radio Advisory Committee (IRAC). The IRAC, its related subcommittees, and ad hoc groups provide information and coordinate activities that help NTIA plan for future RF requirements, assign frequencies, and resolve conflicts.

The spectrum management procedures adopted by NTIA and FCC under the various laws have worked effectively in the past. There have been no major requirements for spectrum use that have not been satisfied. However, not all spectrum requirements have been satisfied with the original frequencies or bandwidths that were requested. Requirements for new spectrum uses have substantially increased in the past decade and it is expected that requirements for new spectrum requirements will continue to increase in the next decade as discussed above. Policy to accommodate these new requirements needs to be adopted.

There has been agreement over some time that there is a problem in government telecommunications policymaking. The Computer and Business Equipment Manufacturers Association (CBEMA) recognized this in its comments submitted in response to a Notice of Inquiry conducted by NTIA in 1982:

The Executive branch of the U.S. government, as currently structured, is designed to deal with well bounded problems and policies... However, it is ill-equipped to deal with problems and policies which cut across the boundaries of those areas of the agencies chartered to deal with them. The existing executive agencies lack the charter of experiential background necessary to deal with issues of the contemporary technology involving international channels for information, the information that flow in those channels, and the processes which might occur during transit.

The NTIA published a report, "NTIA TELECOM 2000, Charting The Course For A New Century", in October 1988.⁶ This report was a general and broad review of the nation's telecommunications, and the trends envisioned in the next century. The main area in the report that is germane to the subject of this paper is the International and Domestic Policymaking in the Year 2000. In this area, three fundamental defects in the current

organizational policymaking structure and process were noted: (1) very short term and reactive, (2) dispersed resources, and (3) absence of focused responsibility. The NTIA report discusses in depth the various aspects of this problem and describes various solutions that have been proposed. These include locating a central policy making organization in the Department of Commerce, or the Executive Office of the President as a special Advisory or Office of Telecommunications Policy, or as recently proposed as a "Council of Communications advisers."⁷ It is clear, that what is required is a centralized telecommunication policy leadership no matters where the location.

In addition to creating a high level centralized policy leadership there also needs to be changes to the short-term and long-term spectrum planning procedures. As previously discussed the spectrum is divided between the government and non-government users with approximately 90% of the spectrum being shared by both groups. Since a large portion of the spectrum is shared and because the introduction of new systems is "time critical," the planning process must be accelerated. The introduction of a new system takes a minimum of approximately two years. The key to accelerated planning is accurate data on present frequency assignments, forecasts of future spectrum use, sophisticated analysis procedures to display spectrum use and closer coordination between the FCC and NTIA in the planning process. This requires an expanded formal coordination procedure between NTIA and FCC that continually looks at short range and long range spectrum problems. Since this planning process requires staffing and computer resources to become effective, legislative action may be required. This enhanced spectrum planning function may also require changes to the Communications Act.

Management Structure

There are certain basic requirements to effective spectrum management that include keeping complete records of frequency usage and effectively coordinating the use of the spectrum between the users. The foreign spectrum management structure that has a single government agency to manage telecommunications but does not maintain centralized data records of all frequency usage is not maintaining the cornerstone of spectrum management. While many countries have a single spectrum management authority they do not maintain records for all users or do not have easily accessible records for all users. In addition, since the authority is actually divided between different services, the critical coordination between users that is required to effectively manage the spectrum is not present. In the United States, although the responsibility is split in the different frequency bands for exclusive or shared usage, data bases that contain frequency assignment records for all services are maintained by NTIA and FCC and there is a formalized coordination of frequency assignments between government and non-government users. The structure is therefore effective in doing basic spectrum

management. Problems may, however, occur in the accuracy of the data as well as the effectiveness of planning for future spectrum use between government and non-government users. The overall conclusion is, that the system does work effectively and if there are shortcomings in the system that we should fix those problems and not throw out an overall very effective system.

NTIA's primary source of spectrum advice is the Interdepartment Radio Advisory Committee, or IRAC, representing major Federal Government users of the radio spectrum. The IRAC has been in existence since June 1, 1922. The IRAC and its subcommittees provide their recommendations to NTIA. NTIA considers this advice and provides approval or disapproval. There are 23 major Federal agencies that are responsible for developing and acquiring radiocommunications to serve their respective missions. As a block of spectrum users, they have significant influence over setting policy in the U.S. The FCC maintains a liaison with the IRAC to represent non-Federal Government interests as shown in Figure 2.

The NTIA is directed by the Assistant Secretary of Commerce for Communications and Information. The main staff element in NTIA concerned with spectrum matters is the Office of Spectrum Management that is headed by an Associate Administrator (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Office of Spectrum Management

The structure of NTIA's spectrum management activities has been described in detail because this structure simply reflects the basic functional elements required for effective spectrum management. There is an element concerned with frequency assignment, frequency records management, engineering analysis, spectrum monitoring and spectrum planning. In order to effectively manage radio frequencies in the future, more attention needs to be addressed to planning for new radio systems and services⁸. In order to accomplish this, there needs to be a new common spectrum planning process between NTIA and FCC. This means close and detailed coordination between a centralized

planning section at the FCC (that does not presently exist) and the Spectrum Plans and Policies Office of NTIA. This does not require a change to the basic structure of either agency.

One final element that is needed to tie the spectrum users with this process is to have a group that advises the spectrum planning function. This group would be composed of private sector and government experts from the various services. The advisory group could also review plans for the solution to new spectrum requirements.

Spectrum Management

Previous sections have described the regulatory procedures and structure of Spectrum Management in the U.S. This section discusses some of the key management/administrative factors that must also be implemented to make certain that the spectrum is used efficiently and effectively in the 21st Century.

Spectrum Mapping

NTIA has used various methods of measuring and graphically presenting how the spectrum is used by, or denied to another system or systems. The basic methods involve presenting Government Master File (GMF) data in such forms as transmitter/receiver location diagrams and GMF data statistics. The GMF data can then be used with a manual or automated frequency-assignment procedure to select a new transmitter frequency, to plan for near- and far-term spectrum use and to aid in the resolution of interference problems. In addition, NTIA has used a denied-area concept to develop restricted frequency area maps to assign frequencies to mobile platforms. These maps, referred to as ATTIC⁹ maps (An Automatic Technique for Calculating Interference from Airborne Transmitter to Terrestrial Receivers), were used as aids in establishing the effective sharing of frequencies and geographical areas in selected bands in the mobile and fixed services. This technique essentially shows how a slice of a frequency band is used. The paper on "Quantification of Spectrum Use"¹⁰ describes a technique to use to measure how much of a frequency band is used or available for new spectrum applications. This technique needs to be applied across the radio spectrum, where applicable, for both government and non-government use of the spectrum to determine how much of the resource is potentially available for other applications.

Frequency Assignment Methods

A number of fast solutions to the problem of assigning frequencies have been described in CCIR Report 842-1. Although the solutions described are not optimum solutions to the frequency assignment problem, the algorithms allow frequencies to be assigned efficiently so that an arbitrary set of frequency-distance separation rules are satisfied that minimize the total bandwidth needed. In most cases these procedures have yet to be used in the day-to-day process of assigning frequencies. These procedures need to be

part of the day-to-day frequency assignment process in order to make the most efficient use of the spectrum.

Spectrum Sharing

Increased spectrum requirements can only be met in the future by also sharing the spectrum more effectively. The fixed or limited spectrum-space resource can be defined mathematically in terms of (1) frequency bandwidth, (2) time duration, and (3) the geometric or three dimensions of space required to describe the signal use area. The geometric space is usually an area although it could be a volume, a line or an angular sector around a point. Many systems transmit continuously so that the time factor may be eliminated.

The basic technical, operational and administrative procedures that should be considered to effectively share the spectrum vary from simple deterministic procedures to complex statistical simulations of operational characteristics. All the complex sharing procedures of the future will probably require computer automated procedures. Successfully sharing of the spectrum will not be limited by technical constraints or computational methods but rather by radio service requirements that limit agreement on acceptable criteria between services. This problem will focus on, but not be limited to, the signal-to-interference protection ratios for the shared services. Without a joint FCC/NTIA planning committee it will be difficult to effectively guide agreements between radio services for increased spectrum sharing.

Spectrum Efficiency Incentives

One of the major ways of increasing the use of the radio spectrum is to change to equipment that are more efficient in the use of frequency, area or time. Typical examples include changing from wideband FM (30 kHz) to narrowband FM (15 kHz) or to a form of SSB such as ACSB that employs a bandwidth of 5 to 7.5 kHz. Another example is that of a trunking system for land mobile that uses the time domain more efficiently and allows approximately four times as many users for a dispatch type system. However, no matter which of these efficiency type systems could be used, they will not typically be used unless specific regulations are enacted to require their use. Even when no channels are available for new assignments, systems users would typically prefer to change to another band then change to the use of more efficient technology. Therefore, another major way of increasing the efficient use of the spectrum is to change to more efficient equipment as equipment is replaced and to require that all equipment be changed by a given date.

International Spectrum Co-Ordination

The process of international spectrum co-ordination also needs to be examined for more efficient use of the spectrum. Satellite and HF frequencies are notified to the ITU/IFRB for protection from possible interference. Frequency assignments with Canada and Mexico are coordinated to protect

their use. The notification and coordination of these types of frequencies is extremely important to all countries. Are there changes to the radio regulations and or the spectrum management structure that can be made to improve the notification and coordination process?

The problem of agreeing to new spectrum policy is now more complex because of the difficulty of reaching international agreement on the introduction of new technology, through the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) process. The ITU affects telecommunication development by the agreements that are reached in radio conferences and the radio standards that are set in the International Radio Consultative Committee (CCIR) meetings. In addition, the ITU is also developing a large program of technical assistance to developing countries through the Telecommunication Development Bureau (BDT) that directly affects telecommunications development in developing countries and indirectly affects the ITU process. Since the budget of the ITU has basically remained fixed, the budget of the other operating units of the ITU have been reduced in order to fund the BDT department. This means that the work of frequency notifications, conference preparations and the CCIR must be accomplished with reduced budgets. In order for the basic work to be accomplished, the working methods of all units need to be made as efficient as possible. Consequently, a "High Level Committee" is reviewing the overall working methods of the ITU, the CCIR is developing new working methods for more efficient introduction of recommendations and the CCIR and the ITU will probably approve committees to examine "Improved use of the radio frequency spectrum and simplifications of the Radio Regulations." U.S. national spectrum management must ensure that the basic functions of the ITU are accomplished in an effective and timely manner and that if the review of the various ITU structure elements is not effective that other solutions are addressed that include increased funding for the ITU.

Another problem that needs attention is technical assistance to developing countries in the field of radio communications. The U.S. has developed programs such as the United States Telecommunications Training Institute (USTTI) and direct bilateral assistance in spectrum management training that have been effective. This type of technical assistance should be continued and increased.

The ITU serves as the principle focus for International Telecommunications and as such must also increase its efficiency in developing new spectrum policy and spectrum standards for the 21st century. In particular, the Radio Regulations need to be simplified, the working methods of the ITU activities needs to be made efficient and accelerated procedures for the adoption of CCIR Recommendations approved.

Summary

This paper summarizes the authors preliminary views concerning an investigation of the U.S. spectrum management structure and the adoption of new management and planning methods to introduce new technology requirements in the Twenty First Century. In order to develop an effective system for the Twenty First Century, it is not necessary to discard the present system, that has worked effectively in the past, but only to modify it in the areas that directly effect the timely adoption of new policy and procedures. This requires 1) "High Level" centralized telecommunications policy leadership; 2) Coordinated spectrum planning between NTIA and FCC; 3) Common NTIA and FCC data base and analysis capability for frequency assignment planning information; 4) A Private Sector Advisory Planning Group and 5) Adoption of spectrum management procedures that includes, spectrum mapping, automated frequency assignment techniques, increased spectrum sharing, flexible spectrum standards and requiring the use of spectrum efficient techniques wherever possible. In addition, the international radio regulations need to be simplified, the ITU working methods need to be made more efficient and accelerated procedures adopted for the approval of CCIR Recommendations. The adoption of the improvements to the spectrum management system described in this paper will require considerable debate over the next few years but will result in the future in flexible and timely approval of new telecommunication systems.

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